

Lacsonian Information Technology Graduates: A Tracer Study

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Abstract

This study determined the employment profile of the Bachelor of Science in Maritime Information Technology (BSMIT) and Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) graduates of John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc. (JBLFMU-Molo). Respondents of this study were the 40 graduates of eight batches from 1998 to 2015. This study utilized the frequency count, percentage, and mode for data analysis. Results revealed that most of the respondents were employed and obtained regular employment. Majority of them were on their subsequent employment and obtained the first employment one month to six months upon graduation. Differences in the relative frequency on the employment characteristics namely, employment status, employment type, status of the latest employment, and length of time acquiring the first job between male and female, and single and married respondents were observed.

Introduction

Information technology plays an important role in education. New and emerging technologies challenge the traditional teaching-learning process, including the way things are managed and controlled. Nowadays, communications provide instant access to a vast array of data. Moreover, technology has opened new markets, new products, new services, and efficient delivery channels for the banking industry. (Macatangay, 2013).

It all started on September 18, 1993 when the John B. Lacson Foundation (JBLF) was born with four separate units including John B. Lacson Colleges Foundation- Molo, presently known as John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University-Molo, Inc. (JBLFMU-Molo) with Associate in Marine Engineering and Bachelor of Science in Customs Administration (BSCA). It was on August 23, 1993 when the unit granted government recognition to offer Maritime High School (MHS) program. In 1994, the government granted the unit a recognition for the 4-year Bachelor of Science in Marine Engineering (BSMarE) program. In 2001, the unit was awarded a full autonomy status by CHED and gave birth to Bachelor of Science in Tourism (BST) and Bachelor of Science in Computer Engineering (BSCOE). In 2002, the unit gave birth to Bachelor of Science in Cruise Ship Management (BSCSM). In the opening of classes in June 2003, the unit started offering the Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) program (“JBLFMU Molo”, n.d.).

BSIT was offered at JBLFMU-Molo starting the academic year 2003-2004. However, it was renamed to Bachelor of Science in Maritime Information Technology (BSMIT) and the curriculum was revised effective academic year 2005-2006. A revised curriculum of BSMIT was implemented starting academic year 2007-2008 in compliance to Commission on Higher Education Memorandum Order (CMO) Number 53, series of 2006. Another revised BSMIT curriculum was implemented starting academic year 2010-2011 in compliance to the renaming of

Filipino courses. The program was renamed back to BSIT effective academic year 2011-2012 containing the same curriculum. However, a revised BSIT curriculum was implemented starting academic year 2012-2013 containing specialization courses.

The first batch of IT graduates was in 2007. As of this time, ten batches of IT students graduated at JBLFMU-Molo but no tracer study has been conducted yet. Hence, this study was done.

The alumni are considered as the best evidence of a program's effectiveness in terms of employment and positions held. Moreover, they are good source of feedback regarding the program's relevance in the current labor market (Orejana et al., 2010).

Tracer studies provide an avenue to analyzing university graduates in relation to the labour market. Tracer studies provide information regarding not only the employability of graduates but also the type of employment they gain; a match or mismatch between educational qualifications and the required work skills and shortfalls of an educational program which helps in aligning the university training to the needs of the economy (Schomburg, 2003).

This study was conducted to trace graduates of BSMIT/BSIT of JBLFMU-Molo. Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of this study. Independent variables include the personal factors of student such as sex and civil status. The dependent variable is the employment profile of the IT graduates of JBLFMU-Molo.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This study determined the employment profile of BSMIT/BSIT graduates of JBLFMU-Molo. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions.

- 1) What is the employment profile of IT graduates when taken as a whole?
- 2) What is the employment profile of IT graduates when grouped according to sex and civil status?

Delimitation of the Study

Although this study aimed to include graduates of batch 2007 to 2015, only graduates from 2008-2015 responded. A total of 40 graduates were considered as respondents of this study.

The data collection happened from June 2015 to May 2016. Only those survey instruments with complete information were considered in the data processing. Data used were taken from the tracer study instrument of the University. Only selected data were included in the processing. Statistical tools used for data analysis were frequency count, percentage, and mode.

The employment profile considered in this study includes the following only: a) employment status whether unemployed or employed; b) employment type whether regular, temporary, or self-employed; c) status of the latest employment whether first job, subsequent employment, or never been employed; and d) length of time acquiring the first job whether less than a month, one month to six months, more than six months to one year, or more than one year.

Methodology

This study made use of the descriptive research design, specifically the survey.

Respondents of the Study

Out of the ten (10) batches of IT graduates, only from 8 batches of graduates responded to this study. These graduates were from batches 2008-2015. Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Category	n	%
Entire Group	40	100.0
Batch		
2008	5	12.5
2009	4	10.0
2010	2	5.0
2011	2	5.0
2012	8	20.0
2013	7	17.5
2014	8	20.0
2015	4	10.0
Sex		
Female	17	42.5
Male	23	57.5
Civil Status		
Married	6	15.0
Single	34	85.0

A total of 40 graduates were involved in this study. Of these, six (6) were hearing impaired. In terms of batches, five (5), four (4), two (2), two (2), eight (8), seven (7), eight (8), and four (4) were graduates of 2008, 2009, 2010, 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014, and 2015 respectively. When grouped according to sex, 17 were female while 23 were male. As to civil status, six (6) were married while 34 were single.

Instrumentation

This study utilized the tracer study instrument of the University. Although the instrument contained much information to fill in, only the following data were retrieved: name, batch, sex, civil status, and select employment profile.

The employment profile considered are the following: a) employment status whether unemployed or employed; b) employment type whether regular, temporary, or self-employed; c) status of the latest employment whether first job, subsequent employment, or never been employed; and d) length of time acquiring the first job whether less than a month, one month to six months, more than six months to one year, or more than one year.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were utilized in analyzing the data. Frequency count was used to determine the number of observations based on certain characteristics. Percentage was used to determine the number of observations based on certain characteristics against the total number of respondents. Mode was used to determine the most frequently observed value of certain characteristics.

Results and Discussion

Table 2 shows the employment profile of the IT graduates when taken as a whole.

Five (12.50%) of the respondents were unemployed, while 35 (87.50%) were employed. Of these employed respondents, 25 (71.34%) were regular, nine (25.71%) were temporary, while one (2.86%) was self-employed.

Of these 40 respondents, one (2.50%) has never been employed, ten (25.00%) said that their present job was their first job, while 29 (72.50%) said that their latest employment was not their first job. Of the 39 respondents who had been employed, 10 (25.64%) of them acquired their first job in less than a month after graduation, 15 (38.46%) acquired their first job after a month to six months upon graduation, eight (20.51%) got the first employment more than 6 months to one year upon graduation, while six (15.38%) acquired the first employment more than one year after graduation.

Most of the respondents were employed and obtained regular employment. Majority were on their subsequent employment and obtained the first employment one month to six months upon graduation.

Table 2

Employment Profile of IT Graduates When Taken as a Whole

Category	f	%
Employment Status		
Unemployed	5	12.50
Employed	35	87.50
Employment Type		
Regular	25	71.43
Temporary	9	25.71
Self-employed	1	2.86
Latest employment		
Never been employed	1	2.50
First Job	10	25.00
Subsequent	29	72.50
Length of Time Acquiring the First Job		
Less than a month	10	25.64
1 month to 6 months	15	38.46
More than 6 months to 1 year	8	20.51
More than 1 year	6	15.38

Table 3 shows the employment profile of the IT graduates when grouped according to sex.

Out of the 17 female respondents, one (5.88%) was unemployed, while 16 (94.12%) were employed. Of these employed female respondents, 13 (81.25%) were regular, while three (18.75%) were temporary.

Of these 17 female respondents, four (23.53%) said that their present job was their first job, while 13 (76.47%) said that their latest employment was not their first job. Of the 17 female respondents who had been employed, two (11.76%) of them acquired their first job in less than a month after graduation, eight (47.06%) acquired their first job after a month to six months upon graduation, while seven (41.18%) got the first employment more than 6 months to one year upon graduation.

Most of the female respondents were employed and obtained the regular employment. Majority of them were on their subsequent employment and acquired the first job one month to six months upon graduation.

Out of the 23 male respondents, four (17.39%) were unemployed, while 19 (82.61%) were employed. Of these employed male respondents, 12 (63.16%) were regular, six (31.58%) were temporary, while one (5.26%) was self-employed.

Of these 23 male respondents, one (4.35%) has never been employed, six (26.09%) said that their present job was their first job, while 16 (69.57%) said that their latest employment was not their first job. Of the 22 male respondents who had been employed, eight (36.36%) of them acquired their first job in less than a month after graduation, seven (31.82%) acquired their first job after a month to six months upon graduation, one (4.55%) got the first employment more

than 6 months to one year upon graduation, while six (27.27%) obtained the first job more than one year after graduation.

Most of the male respondents were employed and obtained the regular employment. Majority of them were on their subsequent employment and acquired the first job less than a month upon graduation.

Table 3
Employment Profile of IT Graduates When Grouped according to Sex

Category	Female		Male	
	f	%	f	%
Employment Status				
Unemployed	1	5.88	4	17.39
Employed	16	94.12	19	82.61
Employment Type				
Regular	13	81.25	12	63.16
Temporary	3	18.75	6	31.58
Self-employed			1	5.26
Latest employment				
Never been employed			1	4.35
First Job	4	23.53	6	26.09
Subsequent	13	76.47	16	69.57
Length of Time Acquiring the First Job				
Less than a month	2	11.76	8	36.36
1 month to 6 months	8	47.06	7	31.82
More than 6 months to 1 year	7	41.18	1	4.55
More than 1 year			6	27.27

Table 4 shows the employment profile of the IT graduates when grouped according to civil status.

All of the six married respondents were employed. Of these married female respondents, five (83.33%) were regular, while one (16.67%) was temporary.

Of these six married respondents, all said that their latest employment was not their first job. One (16.67%) of the married respondents acquired their first job in less than a month after graduation, three (50.00%) acquired their first job after a month to six months upon graduation, while two (33.33%) got their first employment more than 6 months to one year upon graduation.

All married respondents were employed and most of them obtained the regular employment. All of them were on their subsequent employment and most of them acquired the first job one month to six months upon graduation.

Out of the 34 single respondents, five (14.71%) were unemployed, while 29 (85.29%) were employed. Of these employed single respondents, 20 (68.97%) were regular, eight (27.59%) were temporary, while one (3.45%) was self-employed.

Of these 34 single respondents, one (2.94%) was never been employed, ten (29.41%) said that their present job was their first job, while 23 (67.65%) said that their latest employment was not their first job. Of the 33 single respondents who had been employed, nine (27.27%) of them acquired their first job in less than a month after graduation, 12 (36.36%) acquired their first job after a month to six months upon graduation, six (18.18%) got the first employment more than 6 months to one year upon graduation, while another six (18.18%) obtained the first job more than one year after graduation.

Most of the single respondents were employed and obtained the regular employment. Majority of them were on their subsequent employment and acquired the first job one month to six months after graduation.

Table 4
Employment Profile of IT Graduates When Grouped according to Civil Status

Category	Married		Single	
	f	%	f	%
Employment Status				
Unemployed			5	14.71
Employed	6	100.00	29	85.29
Employment Type				
Regular	5	83.33	20	68.97
Temporary	1	16.67	8	27.59
Self-employed			1	3.45
Latest employment				
Never been employed			1	2.94
First Job			10	29.41
Subsequent	6	100.00	23	67.65
Length of Time Acquiring the First Job				
Less than a month	1	16.67	9	27.27
1 month to 6 months	3	50.00	12	36.36
More than 6 months to 1 year	2	33.33	6	18.18
More than 1 year			6	18.18

Conclusions

IT graduates of JBLFMU-Molo are highly employable and obtained regular employment. This may be attributed to the knowledge and skills they possess or they may not be selective of the kind of job to acquire. Moreover, they easily obtained employment such that most of them employed within six months upon graduation. This may be attributed to their preparedness for work or eagerness to get employed. However, they seem not to be contented of their first employment; hence, they tend to transfer employment. This may be attributed the kind of work or salary received in their first job, or other personal considerations.

Taking into consideration the relative frequency, it seems that more female respondents are employed and enjoy regular employment as compared to male respondents. However, more

female respondents seem not stay in their first employment and acquired their first job longer than male respondents.

The relative frequencies show that married respondents are more likely employed and obtained regular employment over the single ones. This may be attributed to the fact that married respondents need to provide financial support to their respective family. Moreover, married respondents tend to find another job; maybe because they need to look for a greener pasture. However, respondents of single status are more likely to acquire job in less than a month than the married ones. This may be because singles are not selective of job and salary since they do not have family to support financially.

Recommendations

Further study has to be made taking into consideration more respondents and applying inferential analysis to ascertain the difference in the employment characteristics between male and female, and between single and married IT graduates.

Another study has to be made to determine the reasons of IT graduates for transferring employment, suitability of work based on their obtained degree, and preparedness to work based on the knowledge and skills they gained from schooling.

Similar study may be conducted taking into consideration other personal factors.

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